

IN VITRO COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF FRACTURE RESISTANCE IN FIBRE-REINFORCED RESIN COMPOSITE RESTORATIONS FOR DEEP CLASS I CAVITIES

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Abstract

Aim: The study compares the fracture resistance of ultra-polyethylene fibre ribbon, fibre-reinforced resin composite EverX posterior, EverX flow, and Tetric N-flow. **Materials and Methods:** Sixty caries-free human mandibular molars were used. The teeth were mounted into acrylic blocks 1 mm below the CEJ. Deep and wide class I cavities measuring 4 x 4 mm were prepared in each tooth. Teeth were randomly divided into 4 equal experimental groups (n = 15) according to restorative material. GI was restored with Ribbond-Ultra with Tetric N-flow, GII, EverX Posterior, GIII, EverX Flow, and GIV, Tetric N-flow. The teeth were stored in 20 ml distilled water at 37°C for 24 hours. The restored teeth were then subjected to thermocycling and fracture resistance testing using a universal testing machine (Instron). The fracture resistance of groups was compared using ANOVA and Tukey's tests. **Result:** The fibre-reinforced bulk fill resin composite (EverX Posterior) exhibited the highest fracture resistance, followed by fibre-reinforced bulk fill flowable resin composite (EverX Flow), and bulk-fill flowable resin composite (Tetric N-flow), while the lowest resistance was observed in teeth restored with polyethylene fibre ribbon and bulk-fill flowable resin composite (Tetric N-flow). Statistical analysis revealed significant differences among the groups, except between EverX Posterior and EverX Flow. **Conclusion:** Contemporary fibre-reinforced bulk-fill resin composites are effective in reinforcing vital teeth against fracture, while utilizing polyethylene fibre ribbon may not hold similar efficacy, regardless of its time-consuming application.

Keywords: Compressive load, EverX Flow, Fibre-Reinforced, Tetric N-flow.

INTRODUCTION

The cutting of tooth structure during cavity preparation decreases its fracture resistance. Restoring carious cavities, fixing dental trauma may require extensive cavity preparation to achieve functional and aesthetic prerequisites without comprising the support needed for the remaining tooth structure¹. Composite fillings are commonly used in posterior dental restorations, whose failure is often attributed to bulk fractures and secondary caries. Direct composite resins provide versatility and aesthetic appeal with excellent bond strength, but require careful application due to their technique-sensitive nature and susceptibility to shrinkage and microleakage. Although time-consuming and prone to air

bubbles and moisture contamination, traditional layering techniques have been standard practice². Bulk-fill composite resins, placable in 4-5 mm thick layers and polymerised in a single step, offer improved fracture resistance³.

Nano-fillers or polyethylene fibres are aimed at enhancing resin composite strength⁴. Fibres can be included in the resin matrix during the material's production process or placed externally during the application of direct restorations⁵.

Ribbon- Ultra is a polyethylene fibre with an ultrahigh elastic modulus, a higher degree of fatigue resistance, and an elastic modulus that is comparable to dentine and allows efficient force transfer, together with easily adapting to the contours of the teeth⁶.

Additionally, Ribbon excels at stress distributions and energy absorption⁷. Short fibres in the resin composite also make it an ideal substructure for reinforcing any resin composite restoration in large cavities⁸.

Fibre-reinforced resin composite restorations serve as fracture stoppers to improve the material's structural qualities. EverX Posterior, premixed fibre-reinforced resin composite of E-glass fibres (9%) permeated into the nanohybrid composite. The average fibre size was 140 µm and a 6 µm diameter.

It has glass filler particles made of barium silicate that are 700 nm in size. It offers superior wear resistance and fracture toughness comparable to dentine due to its numerous short fibres firmly integrated into the resin matrix⁹. Due to the high viscosity and limited aesthetics of EverX Posterior, manufacturers rendered a flowable version for clinical usage that ought to be of superior efficacy. EverX Flow should manifest proper workability as well as improved aesthetical properties, especially regarding the dentine colour.

Owing to the relatively smaller proportions of the particles of its E-glass fibres component and their sizes (0.006 by 0.14 mm), the flowable product demonstrates higher contents of fibres (approximately 25% by weight). Additionally, it was shown to have a lower flexural modulus, easier adaptability in large cavities than EverX Posterior, and improved fracture toughness^{10,11}.

Tetric N Flow offers superior fracture resistance compared to other intra-orifice barriers with excellent flowability, but has limited application in endodontically treated teeth for reducing wear resistance¹². Therefore, this study compares the fracture resistance of dental restorations using Ribbon-Ultra with Tetric N-flow, EverX Posterior, EverX Flow Bulk, and Tetric N-flow. The null hypothesis of the present study denotes the lack of impacting of the fracture resistance upon usage of diverse dental restorations, such as the use of fibre-reinforced composites or ribbons.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials utilised in the present study encompassed a range of products designed for restorative dental procedures, each serving distinct functions and compositions, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Details of used dental materials

Materials	Composition	Manufacturer and LOT No.
Polyethylene fibre (Ribbond-Ultra)	Ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene, Homopolymer H- (CH ₂ -CH ₂) _n -H	Ribbond Inc., Seattle, WA, USA ribbond@ribbond.com 98101
Fibre-reinforced bulk-fill resin composite (EverX Posterior)	Organic content Bisphenol A-glycidyl dimethacrylate, triethylene glycol dimethacrylate, polymethyl methacrylate. Inorganic content E-glass fibres, barium borosilicate glass filler. Filler load (wt, vol. %) 74.2/53.6	GC Corporation, Tokyo, Japan https://www.gc.dental.com 2204111
Flowable fibre-reinforced resin composite (EverX Flow™)	Organic content Bisphenol-A-glycidyl dimethacrylate, tri ethylene glycol dimethacrylate, urethane dimethacrylate, Inorganic Content Micrometer-scale E-glass fibre filler, barium glass Filler load (wt, vol %) 70% by weight, 46% by volume	GC Corporation, Tokyo, Japan https://www.gc.dental.com 2202011
Flowable Bulk Fill resin composite (Tetric N-flow)	Monomer matrix Urethane dimethacrylate, Bis-GMA 27.8% Triethyleneglycol dimethacrylate Inorganic fillers - 7.3 barium glass, ytterbium trifluoride, mixed oxide, silicon dioxide 63.8%. Additives, stabilisers, catalysts, pigments, 1.1%	Ivoclar Vivadent www.ivoclar.com Z0417F
Adhesive (OptiBond™ Extra Universal)	GPDM monomer. Ternary Solvent System (Water, Acetone, Ethanol) acidity drop.	KaVo Kerr www.kerrdental.com 9244546
Enamel and dentine etchant (Meta Biomed)	Phosphoric acid (37%) -H ₂ O -Xanthan gum	Meta Biomed, Chungcheongbuk -do, Republic of Korea. http://www.meta-biomed.com MET2301022

The Research Ethics Committee at Faculty of Dentistry, **University, has approved the present study under the protocol appellation of RECO6U/3-2023 on January 9, 2023. A G-power analysis at $\alpha = 0.05$, corresponding to 90%, and an effect size of 0.544 predicted sample size of 60 samples was determined (15 for each group). Sixty non-carious molars, freshly extracted human permanent mandibular molars extracted for periodontal reasons, were selected and disinfected by immersion in 0.5% sodium hypochlorite solution for 15 minutes. Then, it was cleaned to remove any calculus and soft tissue deposits with an ultrasonic cleaner and examined under 2.5) magnification. The inclusion criteria included

molars with unusual morphology in the occlusal surface, shape, and size to minimise possible confounders.

Defective teeth were excluded, and the remaining teeth were divided randomly into four equal experimental groups, based on the restorative material to be used. Imbuing into distilled water followed to maintain normal humidity, the distilled water was changed every 3 days. The molars were mounted in acrylic resin blocks using specially designed cylindrical moulds, ensuring uniform embedding while leaving 1 mm apical to the cemento-enamel junction. Deep and wide class I design was then prepared in each tooth using a tungsten carbide straight fissure bur (Meisinger, German) and inverted cone bur (Meisinger, German) with high-speed water-cooled handpiece (Dentsply Sirona T4, Sirona Dental Systems GmbH, Fabrikstraße, Germany), standardized to dimensions of 4 mm width and 4 mm depth, and restored with the designated restorative materials according to manufacturer instructions.

After preparing each tooth washing with air-water spray, drying, and etching with 37% orthophosphoric acid 30s for enamel and 15s for dentine. This was followed by priming and bonding procedures using OptiBond™ Extra Universal adhesive. Primer was applied with a micro brush (KaVo Kerr) with agitate motion for 20s then air thin for 5s with medium air pressure according to the manufacturer's instructions. Then, dental adhesive was applied with a micro brush (KaVo Kerr) for 15 s with an agitate motion followed by air thinning for 5 seconds as instructed, and light curing for 10 seconds with a light curing unit (Good Drs - Drs Light CL-AT24 Curing Light, 1200mW/Cm² light intensity, 490 - 440 nm Wavelength) at zero distance. In Group I, cavities were restored using Ribbond-Ultra and Tetric N Flow bulk fill composite, the cavity surfaces were coated with a thin layer of 1 mm of flowable composite resin (Tetric N flow bulk fill) and kept uncured. Ribbond-Ultra was cut to the necessary length (3 mm wide and 4 mm long) with special scissors (Ribbond scissors). Ribbond-Ultra was permeated with excessive bonding agent removed by gentle air drying. Then, the Ribbond was applied, and the fibres were gently pushed with a hand instrument so that they were laminated as closely as possible to the dentine floor and cured for 20s for complete processing of the composite resin. Then, the cavities were restored with Tetric N flow bulk fill resin and cured for 20s following the standardized protocol.

To further reduce the risk of tooth fracturing, a piece of Ribbond-Ultra is placed in the composite approximately 1.5 mm below the occlusal surface of the restoration. Afterwards, the a 1-mm-thick-restoration with Tetric N was performed. In Group II, EverX Posterior fibre-reinforced bulk-fill resin composite was applied directly into the cavity with a 4-mm thickness utilising a specialised gun and curer. Group III, EverX Flow fibre-reinforced bulk fill flowable resin composite was applied into the cavity as one layer 4 mm thick, and cured. Finally, Group IV received Tetric N Flow bulk fill composite restoration was applied similarly. Each group's restoration materials were put on. This detailed approach aimed to standardise the restoration procedures and ensure consistency across all experimental groups, as outlined in previous studies.

Later, diamond finishing burs (Bluewhite / Kerr - FG4255-5) and polishing discs (Soflex, 3M ESPE) were used under air/water spray for a smooth and glossy surface. Subsequently, the restored teeth were stored in distilled water at 37°C for 24 hours to simulate oral conditions. The specimens were then subjected to a thermocycling test (SD Mechatronic Thermocycler, Germany) for 5000 cycles at 5°C–55°C, simulating six months of oral exposure, to evaluate their resistance to temperature changes¹³. Dwell time was 30s, and the bath transition time was 5 seconds. Finally, the fracture resistance analysis was conducted using an Instron universal testing machine model 3345 England, where each specimen was subjected to continuous static load using a stainless-steel ball 5 mm diameter attached to the upper moveable head of the testing machine. The axial compression mood of force applied at a crosshead speed of 1.0 mm/min up to specimen failure, with the force required for failure (Newton) was recorded by machine software. By calculating ANOVA analysis and post-hoc Tuckey's testing, the restoration materials associated with higher fracture resistance were compared, assuming a minimal effect of adhesive bonding efficacy, discrepancies among molar morphology, and cavity preparation design, given that all cases were class I. The variations in maximum compressive load among different restorative techniques underscore their varying effectiveness in enhancing fracture resistance¹⁴.

RESULTS

For descriptive statistics, Group I, restored with Polyethylene Ribbon Fibre (Ribbond-Ultra) with Tetric N-flow, exhibited a mean maximum compressive load of 1075.52 ± 31.67 N, with a range between 1026.55 N and 1124.30 N. In comparison, Group II, restored with EverX Posterior, showed a higher mean maximum load of 1984.32 ± 30.24 N, ranging from 1936.15 N to 2032.25 N. Group III, restored with fibre-reinforced EverX Flow Bulk, had a mean maximum load of 1951.64 ± 33.36 N, with values ranging between 1898.40 N and 2004.50 N. Finally, Group IV, restored with Tetric N-flow, exhibited the lowest mean maximum load of 1479.39 ± 63.11 N, ranging from 1383.60 N to 1575.45 N. These findings highlight variations in fracture resistance among the different restoration materials.

The highest mean of maximum compressive load was observed in Group II, where EverX Posterior displayed a mean compressive load of 1984.32 ± 30.24 N, followed by Group III, restored with EverX Flow demonstrated a mean load of 1951.64 ± 33.36 N, while Group IV, utilizing Tetric N-flow, displayed a lower mean load of 1479.39 ± 63.11 N. Group I, restored with Ribbond-Ultra_PRF and Tetric N-flow, exhibited the least mean fracture resistance at 1075.52 ± 31.67 .

ANOVA and Tukey's computations indicated a remarkable compressive load among the four groups ($p < 0.001$), except for Groups II and III ($p = 0.36$). The mean difference in maximum compressive load between Groups II and I was -908.8 N. The maximum compressive load of Group II was higher than that of Group I ($p < 0.001$). The mean difference in maximum compressive load between Groups III and I was -876.12 N. There was a significant increase in the maximum compressive load of Group III compared with

that of Group I ($p < 0.001$). The mean difference in maximum compressive load between Groups IV and I was -403.87 N. The maximum compressive load of Group IV was higher than that of Group I ($p < 0.001$). The maximum compressive load between Groups II and III was 32.68 N ($p = 0.36$), between Groups III and IV was 472.25 N while that pertaining to Groups II and IV was 504.93 N. Statistically speaking, higher Group II values than Group IV was significant ($p < 0.001$) and between Group III versus Group IV ($p = 0.001$). Visualisation of these findings is depicted in Table 2 and illustrated in Figure 1.

Table 2: Comparison of maximum compressive load among the four groups

Maximum compressive load (N)				F- value	p-value
$\bar{X} \pm SD$					
Group I (n=9)	Group II (n=9)	Group III (n=9)	Group IV (n=9)		
1075.52 \pm 31.67	1984.32 \pm 30.24	1951.64 \pm 33.36	1479.39 \pm 63.11	956.28	0.001
Multiple comparisons (Tukey's test)					
	MD	95% CI		p-value	Significance
		Lower bound	Upper bound		
Group I vs Group II	-908.8	-962.29	-855.32	0.001	S
Group I vs Group III	-876.12	-929.60	-822.64	0.001	S
Group I vs Group IV	-403.87	-457.35	-350.39	0.001	S
Group II vs Group III	32.68	-20.80	86.17	0.36	NS
Group II vs Group IV	504.93	451.45	558.42	0.001	S
Group III vs Group IV	472.25	418.77	525.73	0.001	S

Figure 1: Maximum compressive load of groups I, II, III, and IV

DISCUSSION

Tooth fractures, particularly prevalent in restorations involving a substantial portion of the intercuspal distance, highlight the necessity for robust restorative solutions². Fracture resistance determines a material's ability to withstand predetermined loads, influencing its suitability for different masticatory load areas¹⁵. This was evaluated by measuring the maximum compressive load of the resins¹⁴. Because polymerization shrinkage remains a concern, which results in contraction stresses and lowers fracture resistance as well as restoration failure¹⁶, selecting suitable materials capable of compensating for lost tooth structure, improves treatment outcomes¹⁷. Diverse fibre-reinforced composites are among the most significant modified composites because of their ability to strengthen teeth¹⁸. Therefore, this study compared the fracture resistance among the tested restorative materials.

The cusps and ridges of posterior teeth are especially vulnerable to fracture because of their anatomical form, which causes them to deflect under occlusal force during mastication¹. In the present study, the use of extracted natural mandibular molars was attributed to the fact that they are potentially showing a higher incidence of caries progression as well as their gravity-oriented exposure to the heavy occlusal forces^{7,19}. All the teeth were disinfected by immersion in a solution of 0.5% sodium hypochlorite for 15 minutes and cleaned. The distilled water was changed every 3 days. This was done following ISO recommendation ISO/TS11405 for the storage medium of extracted teeth. Distilled water was used as a storage medium to keep the teeth, as this medium causes the smallest changes in dentine over time¹⁹.

In previous studies, cavity depth and design affected stress generation in enamel. Larger restoration volumes correlate with increased stress on the remaining dental structure, with cusp deflection amplifying with cavity depth, especially with a elevated C-factor²⁰. Class I cavities had the highest C-factor when filled with composite resin; therefore, the class I cavity was prepared for the current investigation²¹.

Bulk-filling offers a convenient approach to cavity restoration, allowing for single-layer filling of cavities up to 4 mm thick. Injectable resin composites, available in low-viscosity (flowable) and high-viscosity forms, are beneficial in clinical settings due to their ease of handling and shorter working times²². Optibond eXTRa Universal²³, a two-component bonding agent, boasts unique smart pH technology and a patented formula enriched with the GPDM monomer and ternary solvent system, providing deeper penetration, improved etching, rewetting capabilities, and a uniform adhesive layer. Ribbond-Ultra_PRF^{12,24}, is of superior strength at a thickness of 0.12 mm. Ribbond-Ultra_PRF are treated equivalently²⁵. These fibres are placed either under or over composite restorations to absorb stresses, and augment fracture resistance, particularly in the occlusal third of the restored tooth²⁶. In this study, the cavity surfaces were coated with a thin layer of 1 mm of Tetric N flow before embedding Ribbond-Ultra_PRF to improve the modular elasticity and prevent fracture⁷. After that, Ribbond-Ultra_PRF with a length of 4 mm and width of 3 mm were prepared²⁷, followed by impregnation with adhesive bonding resin. OptiBond™ Extra Universal, as a wetting agent, facilitated all eliding into a combined

structure⁴. Fibre reinforcement resin composites represent materials that demonstrate high toughness properties sufficient to justify their frequent use in operative dentistry. Dentists first used the short fibre-reinforced resin composite as a bulk dentine replacement material²⁸. It is made of short E-glass fibres inserted into a polymer network matrix along with inorganic fillers. Glass fibres are categorised into A, C, D, E, R, and S types based on different chemical composition, Type E-glass fibres, characterised by their electric properties, boast mechanical attributes such as tensile and compressive strength, elastic modulus, and density, contributing to enhanced fracture resistance²⁹. Stress transfer from the matrix to fibres, influenced by fibre length and diameter, coupled with the fibres' ability to impede crack propagation is often responsible for the improved qualities of the fibre-reinforced composite³⁰. As endorsed, EverX posterior²⁷ consists of a semi-interpenetrating polymer network matrix composed of bis-GMA, TEGDMA, and PMMA compounds, with randomly oriented short E-glass and inorganic particle fillers. The second material was EverX Flow³¹, an injectable composite with short fibres introduced to increase dental composite restoration toughness and fracture resistance. It simplified handling and operative steps, thereby improving the treatment's efficacy. Low-viscosity composite resins, Tetric N Flow³² provide higher flow, improved adaptability to the interior wall of the designed cavitation, simpler insertion, and increased elasticity for dental restorations, providing the best overall combination of good material qualities and clinical efficacy. Thermal cycling has been a widely utilised method in dentistry research. It involves repeatedly exposing restorative materials to hot and cold temperatures to mimic the ageing process that occurs in vivo. In this study, the number of cycles applied was 5000, which corresponds to 6 months of clinical function¹³.

Managing fractures of dental restoratives requires paying a rapt attention to many confounders that include crosshead speed, load application device type, and tooth mounting technique³³. In this investigation, a 5 mm stainless steel sphere assessed the fracture resistance. An axial compressive force was applied towards the centre of the occlusal surface. It is also advocated that the use of a 5 mm stainless steel sphere is perfect for measuring the fracture resistance of molars since it makes uniform contact³⁴. Rejecting the null hypothesis was justified by the *f*-value corresponding to the ANOVA testing among the experimental groups ($p < 0.001$).

Tukey testing also demonstrated a statistical significance pertaining to the inter-group comparisons, except for G II fibre-reinforced bulk fill resin composite (EverX Posterior) and G III fibre-reinforced bulk fill flowable resin composite (EverX Flow Bulk). Gürel et al.³⁵ found that restoration of severely compromised premolar teeth using EverX Posterior could be more privileged over G-aenial Posterior or polyethylene woven fibre-reinforced composite techniques. Ozsevik et al.²⁷ showed that EverX Posterior gives higher fracture resistance than G-aenial posterior and Ribbond-Ultra_PRF in root-filled teeth. Garlapati et al.⁷ concluded that endodontically treated teeth restored with EverX Posterior fibre reinforced composite showed superior fracture resistance than Te-Econom Plus and Ribbond with 3M-ESPE. Farahanny et al.⁵ showed that resin composite EverX bulk-fill has a higher fracture resistance than other groups, Sonicfill bulk-fill, and Filtek bulk-fill ($p < 0.05$). Mohan et al.³⁶ emphasised that using EverX Posterior could be more

advantageous and privileged in class II cavities than Filtek™ Z250 and 3M. Also, Taher et al.³⁰ prioritised using EverX posterior short fibre reinforced composite to Ceram-x-SpherTEC and other alternatives.

For EverX flow being a barrier to crack propagation, this was also consistent with Garoushi et al.³⁷. These authors traced similar compressing loads with restorations on intermingling SFC-core (EverX flow) and a surface dental composite layer. Similarly, Gamal et al.²⁸ confirmed the better results attained from EverX flow and Z350 nano-filled composite resins. Magne et al.¹⁰ found no difference between EverX posterior and EverX flow groups. Also, Ranka et al.⁹ detected no remarkable clinical outcome between EverX posterior and EverX flow. Aboobaker et al.³² endorsed that the Tetric N Flow group showed higher fracture resistance than FUJI GC resin-modified GIC and bonded amalgam. In contrast to our results, Goda et al.³⁸ showed that flowable SFRC (EverX flow) has a non-significantly higher fracture resistance than Tetric N flow. This difference is probably attributed to external confounders concerning the composite restorations' placement and smaller effect sizes. Loading parameters (rate, direction, toolkit,..etc) and changes in mechanic-physical attributes secondary to flowability/consistency could affect empirical measuring of structural flaws or defects (e.g. microcracks and voids detectable ultrastructurally) if the effect size is too small. Also, Rahman et al.³⁹ suggested that endodontically treated teeth were enhanced by utilising polyethylene fibre being placed over or under the restoration. Aslan et al.⁴⁰ recommended the usage of Ribbond-Ultra_PRF in pulpless premolars with MOD cavities compared to fibre posts.

Balkaya et al.⁸ advocated the use of Ribbond-Ultra_PRF and Filtek Z550 more than Filtek Z550, and analogous restorations. Agrawal et al.¹⁶ prioritised Ribbond-Ultra_PRF to be placed horizontally on the pulpal and gingival floor, EverX Posterior showed lesser fracture resistance than the Ribbond-Ultra_PRF groups. This controversy may be attributed to differences in ageing time in thermocycling tests in simulating the ageing of biomaterials, differences in resin composite material used with Ribbond fibre, differences in the direction of the force applied, type of tooth, and many other confounders that can affect the results. Choosing direct resin composites in restoring teeth with a minimal tooth structure is multi-factorial, as fibre-reinforced resin composite restorations (Ribbond-Ultra_PRF) need more operator skills, patient cooperation, longer intra-oral time, more procedural steps, and are expensive. The direct bulk-fill fibre reinforced resin composite (EverX posterior) restorations offer less patient cooperation, ease of use, less intra-oral time, fewer procedural steps, and cost-effective.

CONCLUSION

Within the constraints of this investigation, it is possible to conclude the following:

- 1) The contemporary fibre-reinforced bulk-fill resin composite restoration for deep and wide class I cavities reinforces vital teeth against fracture.
- 2) The application of polyethylene fibre ribbon to reinforce prepared teeth is doubtful and time-consuming.

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Authors' Contributions:

Conceptualization, HMHN.; methodology, HMHN; validation, HMHN, And HH.; formal analysis, HMHN, and HH.; investigation, HMHN, and HH.; resources, HMHN and AF.; data curation, HMHN and RROOT.; writing—original draft preparation, HMHN; writing—review and editing, HMHN, And HH.; visualization, HMHN, and HH.; supervision, HMHN; project administration, HH. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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